

District-level Energy Optimisation for Local Energy Communities

ABSTRACT

The Spanish pilot of DEDALUS shows how **district-level optimisation** can support local energy management in a residential energy community. Implemented in La Seu d'Urgell, it combines household-level flexibility, shared battery storage and a dedicated optimisation platform, while also showing that effective rollout depends on **accessible communication, user recruitment and practical familiarisation**.

KEY POINTS

- Deploying interoperable cloud-based platforms to seamlessly aggregate distributed household assets and optimise shared district-level battery storage.
- Combining automated local energy optimisation with user-friendly nudging applications to actively guide residents toward high-renewable and low-cost consumption periods.
- Useful lessons for navigating local regulatory frameworks based on strong simulation-based results on flexibility, and driving active user recruitment in residential demand response.

The Spanish pilot is a **district-level residential demonstration** implemented in La Seu d'Urgell. It combines household-level devices with shared district infrastructure to test local energy optimisation and demand response services at community scale. The pilot includes **12 dwellings** supported by a shared district battery and a collective rooftop PV system, together with smart plugs, gateways, heat pumps and high-frequency smart meters.

INTEGRATED TECHNOLOGIES AND SERVICES

The Spanish pilot combines interoperable tools supporting district-wide energy optimisation:

- **District-level DR and shared battery optimisation** developed and containerised to schedule battery operation for self-consumption and cost optimisation.
- **Cloud-based acquisition and optimisation layer**, collecting and harmonising data from smart plugs, gateways, the battery and high-frequency smart meters.
- **Personalised nudging application**, a fully deployed mobile app providing near real-time notifications on predicted savings (across sunny, cloudy and rainy scenarios) and advising residents on the optimal, low-carbon hours to operate home appliances.

ENGAGEMENT

- The Spanish pilot organised two technical workshops: one in person at **PEUSA headquarters** with **16 professional participants**, and one residential workshop with **6 participants**, purposefully separating the groups to effectively tailor the technical complexity and language of the presentations.
- Actively addressed unexpected user-driven operational challenges, such as residents inadvertently disconnecting their smart plugs, by implementing **continuous, non-technical educational campaigns** on the importance of keeping DR hardware operational.
- Post-test feedback showed a **more positive overall perception** than in the initial assessment, with the increase mainly driven by professional users.
- The pilot also highlighted two key engagement needs: **more time for recruitment** and **simpler, less technical language** for residential users.

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● KEY RESULTS

- Reached **62% aggregated flexibility mobilised**, supported by the automated dispatch of the shared community battery to successfully displace loads.
- Delivered a massive **56% reduction in carbon emissions**, thanks to the battery's active optimisation of renewable energy.
- Boosted the **rate of self-consumption to 59%**, highlighting the critical role of shared energy storage in community-level DR.
- Achieved a **37% building energy efficiency gain** and a **5% reduction in overall energy system costs**, proving the financial and operational viability of the optimisation models.

● REPLICATION RELEVANCE

- Combine distributed household assets and shared district-level storage within one coherent, **interoperable cloud architecture** to successfully deploy and scale community-level demand response.
- Adapt optimisation algorithms to **local regulatory frameworks**, ensuring that district-level DR can incorporate mandatory, country-specific energy-sharing legislation before executing standard day-ahead scheduling.
- **Never assume automatic user uptake**: technical rollout needs to be accompanied by recruitment effort, tailored communication and practical familiarisation.

● RECOMMENDATIONS

- District-level energy optimisation should be designed as an **integrated system** combining household flexibility, shared storage and interoperable data infrastructure.
- **Shared battery control** can generate strong flexibility and cost results, but these should be communicated carefully when they are simulation-based.
- Effective replication also depends on user-facing design: **recruitment, accessible language** and **gradual familiarisation** are essential to support participation and confidence.

REFERENCES

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